

Creating Job Satisfaction through Improving the Quality of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture in Blitar City Government, Indonesia

Mohamad Agus Sabtoni¹, Lilik Kustiani², Pudjo Sugito³

^{1,2,3} University of Merdeka Malang

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ABSTRACT

Civil Servants (PNS). As elements of the state apparatus, state servants bear a hefty burden in carrying out their duties and functions, considering the various phenomena of dynamic changes in the strategic environment in the current era of globalization. Based on these problems, this research aims To determine the description of transformational leadership style, organizational culture, and job satisfaction in the Blitar City Government. To analyze the influence of transformational leadership, organizational culture and motivation on job satisfaction in the Blitar City Government Environment. The population in this study consisted of civil servants within the Blitar City government. Based on data from Regional Personnel Agency Blitar City, in 2022, the number of employees will be 886. Sampling from the research population was done using a proportional random sampling technique. The number of samples in this study used the Slovin formula with an error rate of 10% of 274. This research concludes that Transformational leadership style and organizational culture affect employee job satisfaction at the Blitar City Government. The results of this research are expected to significantly contribute to the development of knowledge relevant to research problems. They are expected to strengthen the body of theories and for further research in human resource management.

Corresponding Author:
Mohamad Agus Sabtoni

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1. INTRODUCTION

Humans are the principal investment in every organization; therefore, they must be managed in such a way. Managing Human Resources (HR) has become very important in this century so that private and government organizations can grow. (Sinambela & Sinambela, 2019). According to Sinambela (2019), the role of HR is very vital. In the millennium century, humans have been positioned as capital with the birth of the Human Capital concept, where humans are seen as a factor that can produce capital, in the sense that quality and well-performing human resources can become significant capital for organizations to be able to provide services and create satisfaction for service users.

Likewise with Civil Servants (PNS). As elements of the state apparatus, civil servants bear a hefty burden in carrying out their duties and functions, considering the various phenomena of dynamic changes in the strategic environment in the current era of globalization. The demands and challenges of working professionally are necessary to answer all problems in terms of public services or public service bureaucracy (Syaifuddin, 2018).

Performance management is a scientific study that helps organizations manage their human resources to produce excellent performance. It has an enormous scope, and one of the instruments is performance assessment. Performance appraisal is a tool used to determine employee abilities, assess and find out whether someone has done their work as a whole, and find out what employees should do to improve their work. For organizations, the results of performance assessments can be used to develop their human resources.

The quality of government apparatus as the primary capital of national development requires improving the performance of human resources to achieve the expected goals. Strategic human resource quality is achieved by improving skills, motivation, development and management of human resource organization. Apart from that, quality human resources are the main requirement for realizing competitive ability and independence. In line with this, the vision in the context of future development in the civil service sector is to prepare professional civil servants able to compete and anticipate rapid developments in various aspects of life to

improve service quality and high performance (Sinambela & Sinambela, 2019).

The relationship between employees and the performance of an organization has become a widespread topic in the last 100 years in academic and practical circles (Wibisono, 2011). They maintain employees at a high level of productivity and performance, as well as maintain their potential to make maximum contributions to the agency or organization. Organizations are always required to develop new methods or effective strategies to achieve these goals (Syaifuddin, 2018).

Work performance and productivity issues are a serious concern for every institution or agency, especially in the public sector. Good performance will undoubtedly guarantee excellent service quality. Therefore, improving service quality through improving employee performance is necessary to realize organizational goals effectively and efficiently (Syaifuddin, 2018).

Performance is the responsibility of every individual who works in the organization. Performance is a reflection of individual performance where each works well, achieves, is enthusiastic and gives their best contribution, which is the answer to the success or failure of the organizational goals that have been set (Fitria & Kusuma, 2014). Performance is very important for organizations, especially employee performance; whether private corporate organizations or government agencies, the expected achievements and good or bad employee performance can influence the organization's overall performance (Ahmadi, 2021). Performance can influence the ongoing activities of an organization. The better employee performance will help the development of an organization.

This research aims to determine the description of transformational leadership style, organizational culture and job satisfaction in the Blitar City Government and to analyze the influence of transformational leadership, Organizational Culture and Motivation on job satisfaction within the Blitar City Government. The practical benefits of this research for agencies can become a guide in determining policy direction and the grand design of transforming the organization's vision into strategic steps to achieve the expected long-term goals. Apart from that, it also provides support for ideas to improve and perfect employee performance systems. Academics are expected to contribute significantly to developing knowledge relevant to research problems. They are expected to strengthen the body of theories and for further research in human resource management.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The grand theory used in this research is the balance theory. Performance is an implementation of balance theory. A person will show optimal performance if they receive benefits and there is stimulation in their work fairly and

reasonably (Indriasari et al., 2018). According to Bernardin and Russell (1993), performance is a record of the results obtained from specific job functions or activities over a certain period. In the definition above, Bernardin and Russell emphasize understanding performance as the result or outcome of a job and their contribution to an organization.

Leadership is a never-ending problem that needs to be studied or researched by all academic and non-academic circles. In a broad sense, leadership can be used by everyone and is not only limited but applies to a particular organization or institution. The definition of leadership is the process of influencing, directing and coordinating all activities of an organization or group to achieve the goals of the organization or group Antonakis et al., (2003).

Apart from this urgency, transformational leadership is expected to bring fundamental changes to the company's organization. This hope then places the figure of the transformational leader as a role model, foundation and central figure in the organization (Chu & Lai, 2011). This is reinforced by the fact that the result of research by Chu and Lai (2011) clearly shows that strong leadership can create change. The paradigm indicates that the pattern of changing something into something else is a work or work that is substantive in the organization (Fischer, 2016).

García-Morales et al. (2012) explained that transformational leadership is constructive- and contributive to subordinates; transformational leaders even motivate their subordinates to do better by what is actually expected of their subordinates, sacrificing their interests for the sake of the organization's interests, which is accompanied by increasing the level of subordinates' needs. To a better level.

Transformational leadership is a process in which leaders and subordinates raise themselves to a higher level of morality and motivation as the spirit of the organization (Kim & Yoon, 2015). According to Caillier (2014), transformational leadership is a situation where the followers of a transformational leader feel trust, admiration, loyalty and respect for the leader, and they are motivated to do more than what was initially expected of them.

Organizational culture is the control and direction in shaping the attitudes and behavior of members in an organization (Birdi et al., 2016). Organizational culture is a system of meaning that contains a set of critical values mutually agreed upon by all organization members, differentiating the organization from other organizations (Abazeed, 2018). Fulfillment of hopes, desires and conformity to values will create energy, a sense of pride, loyalty and passion (Ali, 2020). Organizational culture is a pattern of beliefs and expectations of all members of an organization (Bura et al., 2019). In line with this statement, Chen et. al. (2016) stated that organizational culture is a pattern of shared assumptions as learning to solve problems of external adaptation and internal integration, which is

taught to new members as the correct way to understand, think and feel to solve these problems.

Hasibuan (2014) emphasizes organizational culture as a cognitive framework containing attitudes, values, behavioral norms and expectations held by organizational members. Kroes (2015) emphasizes that organizational culture requires interaction between individuals and elements within it as a collective phenomenon that shapes a person's response to uncertainty and problems that are inevitable in human experience, with these responses being of two types, namely: 1.) The substance of culture in the form of a mutually agreed upon cultural system; 2.) Cultural forms are created from entities in organizations or actions by which members of a culture express, affirm, and communicate the substance of their culture to each other.

Organizational culture can influence the way employees behave, how they describe their work and how they work (Luthans, 2014). Mathis and Jackson (2008) define organizational culture as a system of shared values, beliefs and habits of an organization that interacts with its formal structure to create norms of behavior. Rivai and Sagala (2010) added that organizational culture is a value system that will influence employees' behavior and way of working. Organizational culture can influence behavior and can also be influenced by behavior (Timothy et al., 2019).

Based on various explanations regarding the definition of organizational culture, it can be concluded that organizational culture is a set of values, norms, and behaviors that are patterned and inherited as a distinction between one organization and another. Apart from that, organizational culture can develop in line with member behavior. Organizational culture can shape employee behavior, and employee behavior can shape organizational culture.

According to Vlacseková (2019), motivation is a person's urge to do something, while motive is a need, desire, desire or impulse. Motivation is an urge that an individual has that can stimulate him to carry out actions or something that becomes the basis or reason for someone to behave or carry out an activity related to a job (Timothy et al., 2019). Motivation is a series of attitudes and values that can influence individuals to achieve more concrete things with individual goals (Putra, 2019).

Motivation is defined as encouragement, where encouragement is a movement of a person's soul and behavior to act. At the same time, motive can be said to be a driving force, which means something that can move humans to carry out actions or behavior, and in these actions, there is a specific goal (Suhartini & Nurlita, 2019). According to Timothy et al. (2019), motivation includes various aspects of human behavior or behavior that can encourage someone to behave or not behave.

According to Rosyadi (2019), motivation is the willingness to expend a high level of effort toward

organizational goals, which is conditioned by the ability of that effort to meet individual needs. According to Miao et al. (2019), motivation encourages a person to carry out a certain activity. Therefore, motivation is often interpreted as a factor that drives a person's behavior. Every activity a person carries must have a factor that drives that activity (Mathis & Jackson, 2008).

According to Kurniawan and Heryanto (2019), motivation is an urge to act on a series of human behavioral processes by considering direction, intensity and persistence in achieving goals. According to Rachma (Rachma, 2019), motivation results from a collection of internal and external forces that cause workers to choose appropriate paths of action and use certain behaviors. Ideally, this behavior will be directed at achieving organizational goals.

Rivai and Sagala (2010) say that motivation is a series of attitudes and values that influence individuals to achieve specific things by individual goals. Based on the definition of motivation above, motivation is an impulse to act that arises because it is given by someone to another person or from oneself. This encouragement means that the person becomes a better individual in achieving goals.

Job satisfaction is one form of employee behavior in an organization. Furthermore, job satisfaction can influence work behavior through motivation and enthusiasm, productivity or performance, and other forms of work behavior. This cycle of response-stimulus-response employee behavior always occurs repeatedly and continues to develop. Someone with high job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards their job (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Ardiansyah (2016) defines job satisfaction as an employee's attitude towards work, which is related to the work situation, cooperation between employees, rewards received at work, and matters involving physical and psychological factors.

According to Luthans (2011), job satisfaction is a positive feeling about a job that results from evaluating several job characteristics, including the job itself, salary, supervision, co-workers and promotions. Likewise, Andini (2017) defines job satisfaction as an emotional attitude of being happy and loving one's job, where this attitude is manifested in work morale, work discipline and work performance. Job satisfaction can be felt inside work, outside work and a combination of the two, as explained by Mariati and Mauldin (2018), including job satisfaction within work, which is satisfaction enjoyed by receiving praise for the results of work, placement, treatment, equipment and atmosphere. Good working environment. Job satisfaction outside of work is felt outside of work, such as the amount of remuneration received from the results of work to fulfill one's life needs. Combined job satisfaction inside and outside work is job satisfaction that is reflected through a balanced emotional attitude between the remuneration received and the performance of the work.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research Design

This research is about Employee Performance in the Blitar City Government Environment. This research analyzes the influence of transformational leadership style, work culture and work motivation through satisfaction and employee engagement on employee performance within the Blitar City Government. This research analysis uses Multivariate Analysis.

The type of research used in this research is explanatory research, where the causal relationship between variables will be examined through testing the hypotheses that have been applied. Explanatory research is a situation where a phenomenon can be known and explained. However, it is necessary to study why and how a phenomenon can occur in more depth. Explanatory research aims to find the causes and reasons for an event by conducting hypothesis tests.

3.2 Research Location and Time

The research was conducted in the Blitar Government office environment, namely echelon officials, with consideration of continuous achievement, even amid a pandemic.

3.3 Population and Sample

A population is a collection of elements with specific characteristics that can be used to conclude (Chandrarin, 2017). The population in this study consisted of civil servants within the Blitar City government. Based on data from Regional Personnel Agency Blitar City, in 2022, the number of employees will be 886. Thus, the total population in this study was 886.

Sampling from the research population was carried out using a proportional random sampling technique, namely a random method of taking samples from members of the population without paying attention to the strata in the population. The sample size in this study was drawn using the Slovin formula with an error rate of 10%. Slovin (1960), in Sevilla (2007) determines the sample size of a population using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = number of samples
N = population size
e = margin of error (5%)
n = 273.6 rounded to 274 samples

Based on the Slovin formula above, the number of samples in this study are 274.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

Descriptive analysis is used to describe the characteristics of each variable as measured by several

research indicators. The analysis technique used is descriptive statistics to produce an average (mean) value for each research indicator and instrument. This is then analyzed using regression.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hypothesis in this research will be tested using path coefficient values and t values to see whether there is a significant influence. Apart from that, the results of the path significance test also show the parameter coefficient values (original sample). The parameter coefficient shows the significance value of the influence of each research variable. In this research, researchers used a confidence level of 95% because, according to Indrawati (2015), business research usually uses a confidence level of 95%. The path coefficient score indicated by the T-Statistics value must be above 1.96 for the two-tailed hypothesis. Based on the Path Coefficient and T-statistics in the table above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

4.1 The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

Ho: Transformational Leadership Style has no significant effect on Job Satisfaction

H1: Transformational Leadership Style has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction

The analysis results using Smartpls are presented in the table above with a significance level of 5%. The resulting T statistic value of 3.759 is greater than the t table value (1.96), and the P-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, the results of testing hypothesis 3 are that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that the Transformational Leadership Style significantly affects Job Satisfaction. The Transformational Leadership Style variable on Job Satisfaction has an original sample of 0.197 with a positive direction, meaning that the better the Transformational Leadership Style, the Job Satisfaction will also increase by 0.19795.

4.2 The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction

Ho: Organizational culture has no significant effect on job satisfaction

H1: Organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction

The analysis results using Smartpls are presented in the table above with a significance level of 5%. The resulting T statistical value of 7.715 is greater than the t table value (1.96), and the P-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, the results of testing hypothesis 1 are that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that organizational culture significantly affects job satisfaction. The Organizational Culture variable on Job Satisfaction has an original sample of 0.389 with a positive direction, meaning that the better the Organizational Culture, the more Job Satisfaction will increase by 0.389.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Transformational Leadership Style has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. Djoko Santoso Moeljono (2005) stated that in this case, the process of planning, organizing, leading activities and controlling that is carried out will reflect the management style that applies in the company. From this statement, learning management style requires time for a leader to adapt to its application within the company because each company has a different organizational culture.

In line with the research results, there have been several changes in management in a company that has been around for decades, and this company also has various kinds of leaders at PT. BOSTON, which has the same goal but with different experiences. Because some of them are employees who have worked at the company for more than 20 years, they can understand the organizational culture formed within the company. On the other hand, several new leaders still have different behaviors and characteristics that can influence the organizational culture at PT. BOSTO (Mondy and Noe translated by Djoko Santoso Moeljono, 2005).

5.2 Organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. Without the support of employees or employees who are appropriate in quantitative, qualitative, strategic and operational aspects, an organization or company will not be able to maintain its existence, develop and advance in the future (Rivai, 2014). Organizational culture is indispensable for successful business operations, and knowledge sharing and organizational innovation are critical drivers for gaining competitive advantage (Azeem M. et.al., 2021). In line with research, organizational culture positively and significantly affects job satisfaction (Wulandari and Ratnawati, (2019). Likewise, research results show that Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction have a negative and insignificant impact on employee performance (Angelika et al., 2019).

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, testing the first hypothesis proves that Transformational Leadership Style and Organizational Culture affect employee job satisfaction in the Blitar City Government. Several suggestions can be given based on the research results and conclusions that have been presented, namely for development. The results of this research can enrich the references and concepts of employee performance models. For further research, it is recommended that a study be conducted on variables that have yet to be included in this research. This can be intended so future researchers can use different objects, places and variables.

Officials who carry out their mandate as bureaucratic officials should pay attention to policy principles by organizational values, provide skills training, provide motivation to foster a sense of pride in employees who are their subordinates and make effective work plans so that employee performance increases and for employees, employees should improve skills and competencies in work, and should have a sense of pride in being part of the Blitar City Government employees, and should also be aware that the organization has provided material benefits and other benefits that are not necessarily available in other organizations.

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